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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Comparative Analysis of 3D Shank Kinematics During Walking: Stroke Patients Versus Healthy Individuals

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ABSTRACT This study investigated the 3-axis gait kinematics of people with stroke to healthy individuals. The specific focus was stroke effects on shank movements in the sagittal, frontal and transverse planes. Sixteen stroke patients and sixteen healthy participants walked along a 10-meter walkway at self-comfortable walking speed, with shank angular velocity measured using two gyroscopes integrated into an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU). Gait events in all motion planes, temporal gait parameters, kinematic data, asymmetry indexes (ASI), and Bland-Altman-liked correlations were also computed. Greater diversity gait patterns were observed in stroke patients. Compared with healthy controls, stroke patients showed reduced stance time on their affected side and lower non-affected swing time, causing gait asymmetry, as reflected in higher ASIs. The stroke patients' shank exhibited limited motion in all motion planes resulting in lower angular velocity and displacement. Sagittal plane angular velocity results were validated using intra-subject comparisons that showed good agreement between limbs in healthy subjects. These empirical findings in this study provide evidence that shank-based IMUs are effective in revealing temporal-spatial gait alterations in people with stroke compared to healthy individuals which can be exploited to develop a targeted rehabilitation plan to reduce abnormalities in the stroke patient group.

INDEX TERMS Angular velocity, asymmetry index, gyroscope, motion planes, stroke gait.

I. INTRODUCTION

Stroke is the third leading cause of disability globally among non-communicable diseases (NCDs). In 2025, a Global Stroke Factsheet issued by the World Stroke

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Organization (WSO) reported that the incidence of stroke has increased dramatically with projections indicating that 25% of individuals over 25 years will experience a stroke at least once in their lifetime [1], [2]. One of the most common consequence of stroke is gait impairment, which significantly affects quality of life and functional independence [3], [4]. The severity of gait dysfunction depends on the location and

extent of brain lesion and is traditionally assessed through clinical evaluations such as maximum walking distance or tolerance level [5]. These clinical assessments are subjective and highly reliant on clinician's expertise, leading to variability in evaluation outcomes.

To address this limitation, objective and quantitative gait analysis techniques have been developed to provide more accurate and consistent [3], [5]. These include gait kinematics and kinetics, plantar pressure distribution, and electromyographic activity. Previous research has established that a 3D motion capture system combined with force plates is widely used and considered the gold standard for capturing detailed spatiotemporal gait characteristics of stroke patients [6]. In addition, systems such as the GAITRite walkway and the Pedar force-sensitive insole system have been applied to evaluate gait symmetry, spatiotemporal variables, and plantar pressure distribution [7], [8]. Despite their accuracy, these systems are expensive, require specialized facilities and well-trained personnel, and are typically confined to laboratory settings [9]. Recent advancements in wearable technology offer promising alternatives. Wearable inertial sensors have gained attention for their ability to record gait motion remotely with minimal interference in natural walking patterns [10], [11], [12]. Wearable inertial sensors, particularly inertial measurement units (IMUs), offer several advantages, including portability, compact size, lightweight design, low cost, and capability to accurately capture gait dynamics in real-world settings [9], [11], [13]. Among IMU components, the gyroscope has shown strong potential for detecting gait events by measuring shank angular velocity in the sagittal plane [14], [15]. Several studies have validated gyroscope-based gait event detection by comparing with pressure insole (e.g. F-Scan) and optical motion capture system (e.g. Vicon), demonstrating high accuracy in both indoor and outdoor walking conditions [14], [15]. In 2020, Fadillioglu et al. demonstrated that a single shank-mounted gyroscope could accurately estimate gait events across a range of walking tasks [10]. Their algorithm enabled flexible and precise detection of gait events during free-living activities. More recent study have further supported the reliability of shank-based gyroscope data, showing high agreement with motion capture systems for gait event detection [15]. These methods have proven particularly effective in identifying gait events during normal walking in healthy individuals.

However, most studies on stroke-related gait impairments utilizing gyroscope-based sensors have focused primarily on spatiotemporal parameters in the sagittal plane, offering a limited perspective on stroke-related gait dysfunctions. The primary objective of the present study was to comprehensively characterize three-dimensional (3)-axis shank kinematics by comparing stroke patients with healthy controls. By identifying distinctive shank movement patterns, this study aims to contribute to the development of targeted rehabilitation strategies that can enhance gait function and improve the overall quality of life in post-stroke individuals.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. PARTICIPANTS

Sixteen stroke patients and sixteen healthy participants were recruited from Songklanagarind hospital. Prior to testing, participants were fully informed about the general aims, procedures of the study, and provided written informed consent. Primary inclusion criteria for the stroke patient group were: (1) diagnosed as a chronic stroke with the first onset; (2) older than 45 years; (3) able to walk at least 30 meters without gait assistance or an orthosis with physiotherapist supervision and their medical condition stable; and (4) able to follow the experimental stepping procedures. Potential patients were excluded if they had: (1) musculoskeletal problems six weeks prior to participation, lower limb arthroplasty or a major fall; (2) history of another neurological condition; and (3) heightened fear of falling. Criteria for recruiting healthy participants were over 45 years of age and able to perform daily activities for at least 30 minutes without angina chest pain or falling. They were excluded if they had diabetic neuropathy, a history of lower limb arthroplasty, musculoskeletal impairment due to peripheral nerve damage, or a history of significant fall. Eligible participants who met the criteria were asked to perform the 10-meter walk test on a straight walkway at a comfortable walking speed, under the guidance of a licensed physiotherapist specifically trained in gait testing for stroke patients. Table 1 shows the participants' demographic data and the results of the walking test.

TABLE 1. Demographics of participants.

	Stroke	Healthy
Gender (Male/Female)	11/5	9/7
Age (years)	60.44 (6.97)	60.06 (6.38)
Height (m)	1.65 (0.08)	1.60 (0.08)
Mass (kg)	66.81 (12.31)	59.89 (10.13)
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.55 (3.58)	23.36 (2.78)
10MWT (s)	27.96 (13.51)	9.01 (1.77)
Onset (years)	3.67 (3.41)	-
Affected side (Left/Right)	8/8	-

Values are presented as mean (SD).

B. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The study protocol was approved by Human Research Ethics Unit (HREU) of the Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, and complied with the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki. Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensors (MBIENTLAB INC, San Francisco, USA) were used to sample limb kinematics, with gyroscopes incorporated into the IMU devices measuring the local angular velocity of the shank. Two sensors were placed 25 mm above the malleolus on the lateral surfaces of both shanks similar as in previous studies [15], [16]. Fig. 1 illustrates the locations of IMU sensors and reference frames, where the superior-inferior, posterior-anterior, and lateral-medial directions are depicted as the x-, y-, and z-axes, respectively.

FIGURE 1. Shank-mounted IMU sensor position relative to principal axes.

C. STUDY PROTOCOL

The experiments were performed at the Southern Medical Rehabilitation Center of the Songklanagarind hospital. All participants were instructed to walk back and forth at their most comfortable speed along a 10-meter walkway for two trials. Following this, a 5-minute rest was provided to avoid fatigue effects which could affect gait performance. Each participant repeated this procedure three times.

D. DATA ANALYSIS

MATLAB R2020b was used to derive temporal parameters and gait kinematics from the gyroscope signals. During signal preprocessing, the raw data were filtered to remove dynamic noise using a second-order low pass Butterworth filter with a 35 Hz cutoff frequency [14], [17]. As shown in Fig. 1, the gyroscope data were aligned with sagittal (positive right), frontal (positive backward), and transverse (positive upward) planes. Stance and swing phases were separated by identifying heel strike and toe-off events, respectively [14]. Stance and swing intervals in the frontal and transverse planes were determined based on corresponding intervals in the sagittal plane, with five consecutive gait cycles processed to represent the gait characteristics of both stroke patients and healthy participants.

1) TEMPORAL PARAMETERS

Fig. 2 shows the sagittal plane shank angular velocity during a gait cycle for the healthy group and the stroke patient group. The interval between one positive peak and the next defines the stride time. Stance time is the period from the initial minimum point to the last minimum point before the ascending zero-crossing, while swing time is determined from that last minimum point to the initial minimum point after a descending zero-crossing following the positive peak. The percentages of stance and swing time were calculated using Equations (1) and (2), respectively.

$$\text{Percentage of stance time} = \frac{\text{Stance time}}{\text{Stride time}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Percentage of swing time} = \frac{\text{Swing time}}{\text{Stride time}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

2) KINEMATIC DATA

The continuous waveforms of the gyroscope signals from eight right-affected stroke patients and eight right-side

healthy subjects were used to calculate angular velocity using a root mean square (RMS) calculation. RMS value for all motion planes during a gait cycle can be quantified by,

$$RMS(deg/s) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i^2} \quad (3)$$

where x_i represents an N -length data set of angular velocity in each plane from one gait cycle. The average RMS values during stance and swing phases were determined from 5 consecutive gait cycles. The gyroscope provides information of the shank's movement during stance and swing. Shank motion (θ) was obtained by integrating angular velocity signals over time, as expressed in Equation (4):

$$\text{Degree of shank motion; } \theta(\text{degree}) = \int_0^t \omega(t) dt \quad (4)$$

where $\omega(t)$ is the angular velocity (in degrees per second) over the sampled period. The left-right asymmetry index (ASI) for RMS angular velocity and shank motion in healthy and stroke individuals were calculated using Equations (5) and (6) as follows,

Asymmetry index (ASI) of healthy subject

$$= \frac{|V_{\text{Left}} - V_{\text{Right}}|}{\text{Mean of both sides}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Asymmetry index (ASI) of stroke patient

$$= \frac{|V_{\text{Affected}} - V_{\text{Non}}|}{\text{Mean of both sides}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where V_{Left} , V_{Right} , V_{Affected} , V_{Non} are the values of each parameter for the left, right, affected, and non-affected sides in healthy and stroke individuals respectively. Higher ASI means more asymmetry; zero is perfect symmetry.

3) STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All statistical analysis were performed using Prism9 (GraphPad Software, MA, USA). The Mann-Whitney test was computed to compare all measurements between the stroke patients and healthy participants. Each variable was subjected to pairwise comparisons between the affected and non-affected sides using Wilcoxon's signed rank test. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

In addition, the intra-subject Bland-Altman-liked method [18] was adapted to compare the ratio of RMS angular velocity between the left and right sides for both groups. To illustrate bias and limits of agreement between both limbs, the graphs were created using the mean difference and ± 2 standard deviations (SD) across individuals. This ratio equals one when the variance of both limbs is equal [19]. A narrower range between the limits of agreement indicates better consistency.

III. RESULTS

A. TEMPORAL GAIT PARAMETERS

Temporal gait parameters are reported in Table 2. The stroke group exhibited significantly longer stride times

TABLE 2. Temporal gait parameters.

	Healthy (n=16)		Stroke (n=16)	
	Right side	Affected	Non-affected	
Stride (s)	1.01 (0.09)	1.62 (0.40)*	1.63 (0.39)*	
Stance (s)	0.64 (0.06)	1.00 (0.37) ^{††}	1.17 (0.34)*	
Swing (s)	0.46 (0.03)	0.65 (0.16) ^{††}	0.46 (0.11)	
%Stance	57.94 (1.68)	59.88 (7.76) [†]	71.24 (6.12)*	
%Swing	42.06 (1.68)	40.13 (7.76) [†]	28.76 (6.12)*	

Values are presented as mean (SD).

*p<0.05 Mann-Whitney test comparison with right side of the healthy group.

[†]p<0.05 Wilcoxon signed rank test comparison with a non-affected side.

on both affected and non-affected sides compared to the healthy group. Stroke patients demonstrated significantly prolonged stance time, especially on the non-affected side, and significantly increased swing time on the affected side. Furthermore, significant differences between the affected and non-affected sides were observed in stance time, swing time, and the percentage of stance and swing time over one gait cycle.

B. SAGITTAL PLANE SHANK ANGULAR VELOCITY AND GAIT EVENTS

Fig. 2 presents a typical sagittal plane shank angular velocity profile for a healthy subject and a right-affected stroke patient. The healthy subject had a shorter stance time compared to the stroke patient, both non-affected and affected sides. Regarding swing time, the stroke patient spent a longer duration on their affected side compared to the non-affected side. Additionally, the angular velocity of the healthy group was higher than of the stroke patient, with the affected side of the stroke patient showing lower angular velocity, particularly during swing.

C. SHANK ANGULAR VELOCITY AND GAIT EVENTS IN THE FRONTAL PLANE

The angular velocity pattern of the right-affected stroke patient showed reduced motion during stance on both sides (Fig. 3). Additionally, the swing pattern on the affected side resembled that of healthy participants but with reduced amplitude. In contrast, the non-affected side showed reduced angular excursion and opposite pattern during both stance and swing. In the frontal plane, an adduction was observed on the affected side during initial swing, while the non-affected side showed an abduction.

D. SHANK ANGULAR VELOCITY AND GAIT EVENTS IN THE TRANSVERSE PLANE

Fig. 4 illustrates transverse plane angular velocity across one gait cycle for healthy individuals and stroke patients. During initial contact, healthy subjects exhibited slight external rotation of the shank in relation to their thigh, followed by slow internal rotation. The shank rapidly rotated externally, increasing before stabilizing with an external rotation motion during the single limb support phase of stance.

FIGURE 2. Gait pattern in sagittal plane. It presented three difference characters of a healthy person (top), a right affected side (middle), and a left non-affected side (bottom) of stroke patient. The y-axis depicts shank angular velocity in degree per second, while the x-axis depicts the percentage of time in each gait cycle. The red circles (o) represent the heel strike time whereas red stars (*) represent toe-off time point.

As toe-off ends, the shank rotated internally during the swing phase. In contrast, stroke patients demonstrated mild external rotation at the beginning of stance, maintaining this position until slightly more external rotation on the affected side while non-affected side exhibited internal rotation at toe-off. Subsequently, the non-affected side showed an opposite pattern compared to the healthy and the affected sides, with external rotation primarily occurring during the swing phase. The affected side exhibited lower angular velocity during external rotation and rarely demonstrated internal rotation during swing phase. Additionally, stance time on the non-affected side was longer than that of the affected side.

E. SHANK KINEMATICS

Table 3 summarizes the RMS shank angular velocity and shank range of motion (ROM) during both stance and swing phases. Across all motion planes, the RMS of angular velocity in the stroke group was lower than that in the healthy group. In the sagittal plane, the RMS of angular velocity was significantly lower in the stroke group, for both affected and

FIGURE 3. Gait pattern in frontal plane. It presented three difference characters of a healthy person (top), a right affected side (middle), and a left non-affected side (bottom) of stroke patient. The y-axis depicts shank angular velocity in degree per second, while the x-axis depicts the percentage of time in each gait cycle. The red circles (o) represent the heel strike time whereas red stars (*) represent toe-off time point.

non-affected sides, in both stance and swing phases. Shank rotation angle was higher in the healthy group, followed by the non-affected side and then the affected side in the stroke group. In the frontal plane, the healthy group also revealed significantly higher RMS during both stance and swing phases compared to both sides in the stroke group. As expected, during stance, the stroke group’s affected side had lower shank motion compared to the healthy group and the non-affected side. During the swing phase, the healthy group exhibited significantly greater shank movement, which opposed the movement patterns observed in the stroke group.

In the transverse plane, the RMS of shank angular velocity for the healthy group was significantly higher than the affected side during both stance and swing phases. The significant differences were found only in the swing phase. During the stance phase, stroke patients exhibited a significantly different range of shank motion on both sides compared to healthy subjects. No statistically significant differences in shank motion between groups during the swing phase.

FIGURE 4. Gait pattern in transverse plane. It presented three difference characters of a healthy person (top), a right affected side (middle), and a left non-affected side (bottom) of stroke patient. The y-axis depicts shank angular velocity in degree per second, while the x-axis depicts the percentage of time in each gait cycle. The red circles (o) represent the heel strike time whereas red stars (*) represent toe-off time point.

F. ASYMMETRY INDEX (ASI) OF ANGULAR VELOCITY AND SHANK RANGE OF MOTION (ROM)

As shown in Table 4, stroke patients exhibited a significantly higher sagittal plane ASI than healthy subjects. There were no significant differences in ASI during the stance and swing phases in either transverse or frontal planes. In the frontal plane during the stance phase, the impaired group showed a higher ASI of RMS of shank angular velocity compared to the healthy group. In the transverse plane, stroke patients exhibited higher ASI values of RMS of shank angular velocity and shank motion during both stance and swing phases compared to healthy individuals.

G. BLAND-ALTMAN-LIKED PLOTS FOR RMS SHANK ANGULAR VELOCITY RATIO

Fig. 5 and 6 summarize the left-right RMS sagittal plane angular velocity ratios for the healthy group and the affected-non-affected sides in the stroke group. The left-right angular velocity RMS ratios for healthy participants were 1.02 and 1.01 with limits of agreement from 0.89 to 1.51

TABLE 3. Shank kinematics for healthy controls and stroke patients.

	Sagittal plane (n=8) (ML axis)			Frontal plane (n=8) (Sagittal axis)			Transverse plane (n=8) (Longitudinal axis)		
	Healthy	Affected	Non-affected	Healthy	Affected	Non-affected	Healthy	Affected	Non-affected
RMS of angular velocity in stance (degrees/s)	120.70 (11.51)	47.80* (24.27)	57.20* (21.22)	29.14 (8.66)	20.38* (6.77)	18.39* (6.97)	53.10 (10.53)	29.20* (14.38)	28.10* (10.29)
RMS of angular velocity in swing (degrees/s)	246.90 (19.06)	104.30** (45.11)	164.10* (38.52)	47.21 (23.48)	30.95* (9.83)	32.30* (11.79)	81.79 (16.41)	59.81* (18.29)	72.53 (24.38)
Shank motion stance (degrees)	-63.61 (3.76)	-32.28** (12.41)	-42.60* (13.02)	-3.12 (11.52)	-0.90 (8.99)	-3.12 (7.62)	-14.17 (4.03)	0.02* (8.77)	2.18* (6.34)
Shank motion swing (degrees)	65.50 (4.70)	33.45** (13.89)	42.61* (12.85)	-7.33 (13.82)	3.00* (11.12)	2.78* (9.47)	9.17 (6.07)	3.24 (8.57)	0.63 (16.30)

Values are presented as mean (SD) from eight stroke patients with right-affected side and eight healthy individuals from right side.
 *p<0.05 Mann-Whitney test comparison with right side of the healthy group within each plane.
 †p<0.05 Wilcoxon signed rank test comparison with non-affected side within each plane.

TABLE 4. Asymmetry index (ASI) of shank angular velocity and angular motion.

	Sagittal plane (ML axis)		Frontal plane (Sagittal axis)		Transverse plane (Longitudinal axis)	
	Healthy (n=16)	Stroke (n=16)	Healthy (n=16)	Stroke (n=16)	Healthy (n=16)	Stroke (n=16)
RMS angular velocity in stance	5.66 (3.27)	24.40* (19.94)	24.74 (23.68)	35.55 (21.17)	15.62 (13.58)	20.98 (14.71)
RMS angular velocity in swing	5.27 (3.39)	51.22* (31.58)	38.05 (30.94)	24.98 (31.97)	20.38 (13.88)	30.40 (16.19)
Shank angular motion in stance	5.01 (3.42)	31.79* (15.48)	75.22 (60.34)	73.92 (53.66)	42.56 (36.09)	68.44 (65.81)
Shank angular motion in swing	3.70 (4.27)	30.42* (20.06)	86.98 (64.31)	66.34 (56.98)	83.51 (52.53)	101.70 (65.37)

Values are presented as mean (SD) in percentage difference.
 *p<0.05 using the Mann-Whitney test to compare stroke patients' shank motion with the healthy group's right side.

and 0.88 to 1.13 for the stance and swing phases, respectively (Fig. 5). In contrast, the ratio of angular velocity RMS between the affected and non-affected sides in stroke patients was 0.82 and 0.48, with limits of agreement from 0.46 to 1.18 and 0.40 to 0.56 for stance and swing respectively (Fig. 6). The mean differences in measured angular velocity ratio were approximately 0.20 for stance and 0.53 for swing.

IV. DISCUSSION

Various gait variables, including temporal and kinematic parameters, were used to explore the effects of stroke

on gait control in stroke patients compared to healthy participants. Gait profiles, specifically the movement patterns of shank during walking, were captured using gyroscopes. This study showed that the pattern of angular velocity in the sagittal plane during the gait cycle aligns with the study by Salminen et al. who performed IMU-based gait event detection [15]. Stroke survivors exhibited modified gait patterns, such as prolonged swing times and significant timing asymmetries between the affected and non-affected sides. Although the overall shank movement patterns in stroke patients resembled those of healthy participants, their sagittal

FIGURE 5. Bland-Altman-like plots for average RMS shank angular velocity and RMS shank angular velocity left-right ratios for the healthy group in Stance (a) and Swing (b), each circle represents one individual. The solid line denotes mean RMS ratio, and the dashed lines are the limits of agreement (± 2 SD).

plane angular velocity was significantly lower. Additionally, stroke patients exhibited high variance in sagittal plane RMS angular velocity ratios, indicating greater asymmetry and variability. A particularly interesting finding emerged from the comparison of gait patterns in the frontal and transverse planes. In these planes, the non-affected side of stroke patients showed a pattern that differed not only from the affected side but also from the gait pattern of healthy individuals, suggesting compensatory mechanism or maladaptive motor control strategies [3], [20], [21].

A. TEMPORAL GAIT PARAMETERS

Stroke was shown to have characteristic effects on gait control, particularly on the paretic limb, primarily due to muscle weakness. Stroke patients demonstrated a longer swing phase, and significant changes in gait timing on the affected limb were consistent with previous studies in terms of stride time, stance time, swing time, and the percentage of stance and swing periods within a gait cycle [3], [4], [22]. The results of this study showed that stride time was lengthened on both the affected and non-affected sides in stroke patients. A shortened stance on the affected limb was compensated by a longer stance on the non-affected side. Significant differences in almost all temporal parameters were seen between both sides, possibly due to instability caused by impaired sensorimotor control, which was

FIGURE 6. Bland-Altman-like plots for average RMS shank angular velocity and RMS shank angular velocity affected-non-affected ratios for the stroke patient group in Stance (a) and Swing (b), each circle represents one individual. The solid line denotes mean RMS ratio, and the dashed lines are the limits of agreement (± 2 SD).

compensated by slower walking speeds [6], [23], [24]. Stroke-related impairments in neuromuscular control such as muscle weakness may also contribute to reduced stride length and altered gait symmetry [3], [20].

B. SHANK KINEMATICS DURING WALKING

In this study, IMU sensors were employed to support the development of more practical method for assessing complex gait impairments caused by stroke [3]. Previous study has highlighted the importance of analyzing lower limb segment in the sagittal plane, as it is essential for safe and efficient walking [3]. Our findings demonstrated that body-mounted sensors can effectively identify stroke-related alterations in gait mechanics, as shown through a comprehensive analysis of both linear and angular kinematics across all three principal planes, with a primary emphasis on shank flexion and extension. Efficient shank motion relies on knee joint mobility, typically involving two peaks of flexion: a smaller peak during the stance phase, which assists in shock absorption and forward propulsion, and a later larger peak during swing, which facilitates sufficient foot-ground clearance [20]. Furthermore, our findings align with previous studies indicating that stroke patients exhibit reduced knee flexion in the initial stance, followed by compensatory knee extension in late stance to prepare for foot clearance during swing [3], [25]. These findings support prior observations of knee hyperextension during stance and weakened knee

flexion and extension during swing, on both the affected and non-affected sides of stroke patients [25]. Two flexion peaks observed in the affected side during swing were found in the one third initially and later resulting from overactivity of the rectus femoris and inadequate push-off [20]. Excessive knee flexor activation, possibly due to changes in muscle length and stiffness of knee flexors, may limit knee extension prior to heel strike [3]. In the frontal plane, shank movement is influenced over time by hip abduction and adduction during walking [24].

The current findings support the proposition that the range of shank abduction and adduction is reduced in stroke patients [20]. Our results presented that the RMS values of angular velocity were higher in healthy subjects, reflecting a greater magnitude of shank motion in this plane. In healthy individuals, shank abduction typically begins at the start of the stance phase, transitioning into adduction before foot placement preparing for the next gait cycle. In stroke patients, the non-affected side followed a similar pattern, initial abduction during stance, followed by adduction with the peak occurrence in mid swing. The affected side predominantly exhibited abduction throughout the gait cycle, with only limited transition to abduction in the late swing. Notably, during the swing phase on the non-affected side, shank movement was characterized more by adduction rather than abduction [20]. Focus on the stroke patient group, the mediolateral shank movement was lower on the affected side compared to the non-affected side. The increased abduction and adduction observed on the non-affected side may result from compensatory hip movements aimed to extend the base of support and maintain stability during walking, due to limited motion on the affected side [24], [26]. Our finding aligns with the prior study which suggested that stroke individuals have reduced ability to accurately control over abduction and adduction at the paretic hip [27]. Increased gait variability can lead to gait instability in stroke patients.

In the transverse plane, shank motion involves external and internal rotation. The coordination between the shank and thigh during gait indicates that individuals affected by stroke encounter challenges in shank rotational movement [28]. In healthy individuals, the pelvis, femur, and tibia typically rotate in a same direction with a different proportions [20]. This finding supports evidence from previous observations which showed the external rotation occurs during stance phase, followed by the internal rotation during swing [20]. During single-limb support in the stance phase, the lower limb turns outward to externally to preserve stability. From terminal stance to initial swing, the tibia internally rotates in coordination with the knee flexion to prepare for foot clearance. The observed difficulty in a shank rotational movement resulted from the impact of weakened and spastic muscles, which led to a lack of coordination between the shank and thigh segments [28]. Our study observed that in healthy individuals, the shank exhibited external rotation (14.17 ± 4.03 degrees) during the stance phase, followed by internal rotation (9.17 ± 6.07 degrees)

during the swing phase. In contrast, stroke patients' affected side showed minimal internal rotation during the stance phase (0.02 ± 8.77 degrees) and progressive internal rotation during the swing phase (3.24 ± 8.57 degrees). There were internal rotations of 2.18 ± 6.34 degrees in the stance phase and 0.63 ± 16.30 degrees in the swing phase of non-affected side. Moreover, during walking, a previous study presented that there was a weak coupling between rearfoot eversion/inversion and shank internal/external rotation [29], suggesting that the motion of the knee in the sagittal plane and the motion of the rearfoot in the frontal plane were not necessarily interrelated through transverse shank rotation.

Our finding using gyroscope-based sensors showed stroke patients exhibited lower RMS value of shank angular velocity across all motion planes, particularly in the sagittal plane. These results indicate reduced shank movement in stroke patients compared to healthy subjects. It can therefore be assumed that the RMS of shank angular velocity in the sagittal plane is a key variable for evaluating gait abnormalities. The RMS value, which is associated with magnitude of angular velocity, can be utilized as a reliable metric for monitoring treatment progress. Therefore, the RMS of shank angular velocity in the sagittal plane provides an effective parameter for assessing rehabilitation outcomes and distinguishing gait characteristics between groups. Additionally, the RMS of shank angular velocity in the frontal and transverse planes offer further insight into the unique gait patterns associated with stroke. A previous study also explored the use of rotational segment angles of foot, shank, thigh and trunk segmental angles during gait training as a progress indicator [30].

C. GAIT VARIABILITY

Prior studies noted the importance of the asymmetry indices (ASI), which quantify differences between limbs, for evaluating gait performance in stroke patients. ASI has been used including the differences of the plantar pressure to illustrate the severity owing to stroke, the spatiotemporal parameters or the symmetrical steps for investigating the benefit of gait training protocol [7], [30], [31]. The most striking was the substantial difference in the sagittal plane due to the higher range of shank motion circumstance especially in the RMS values of angular velocity during the swing phase, due to the larger range of shank motion. Our findings align with previous studies, showing that ASI values in the sagittal and transverse planes which express in the stroke patient group higher than the healthy group. Damaged brain in stroke patients resulted in difficulties in regulating neuromuscular control, which subsequently causes alterations in the ASI of gait quality measures across joint kinematics in all motion planes [32]. For the frontal plane, the ASI values are almost higher in healthy subjects than stroke patients. The significant differences in ASI between the groups were only observed in the sagittal plane. However, the stroke patient group had higher ASI values compared to the healthy group. This may be related to the reduced stability observed when stroke patients walk at their comfortable pace [33].

This study presented the Bland-Altman-liked plot to see the agreement of lower limbs in healthy subjects and stroke patients. Therefore, the intra-subject variances were found in the stroke patient group especially in the stance phase due to the difference in a ratio of RMS shank angular velocity from both limbs in the sagittal plane. In the stroke patient group, the scatter of the RMS angular velocity ratio was wider than that in the healthy group due to large difference within individuals and heterogenous patterns. Good agreement between RMS of shank angular velocity in the left-right limb ratio were observed in the healthy group, with values close to 1.00, indicating minimal variation between limbs. Moderate to large correlations were observed in Bland-Altman-liked plots of stance and swing phases in the stroke patient group. According to these data, the findings are consistent with the ASI of kinematic parameters which indicate gait asymmetry among stroke patients. However, in the swing phase, the variation of the ratio of RMS angular velocity in the stroke patient group is slightly less than that in the healthy group which can be a result of muscle weakness and adaptability to compensate the impairment which can prioritize safety over speed.

D. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Our findings are subjected to several limitations. The small sample size, particularly limited to the number of stroke participants, may affect the generalizability of the findings. The data in this study were collected using gyroscope embedded within IMU sensors, however, these measurements were not benchmarked against high-precision motion capture techniques. Additionally, incorporating measures of stroke severity may have assisted in accounting for some of the within-group kinematic variability. Further research to determine the interdependence of lower limb segment kinematics and lower limb muscle activity generated during walking may also assist in better understanding gait complexity among stroke patients, which will be of considerable benefit in the design and evaluation of gait rehabilitation interventions.

V. CONCLUSION

Our study confirmed that stroke patients exhibited a reduced shank angular velocity and range of shank motion across all planes of movement, with the most pronounced impairment occurring in the sagittal plane, which is the crucial component for efficient gait. This reduction is the primary gait characteristic that distinguishes stroke patients from healthy individuals. The clear finding to emerge from this study is the limited knee flexion and extension in stroke patients during both stance and swing phases, resulting in altered shank movement patterns. These changes, particularly in flexion and extension, serve as reliable indicators of walking performance to differentiate the gait of stroke patients from their non-affected side and healthy individuals. In the frontal plane, stroke patients showed reduced abduction and adduction, with greater compensation observed on the non-affected side, likely due to muscle coordination imbalances.

In the transverse plane, shank rotational movement was limited, further contributing to gait instability. Assessing movement in both frontal and transverse planes provides important insights into how stroke affects walking patterns, highlighting the need to consider more than just forward-backward movement when evaluating gait. The ASI highlighted significant disparities in shank movement between the affected and non-affected limbs, particularly in the sagittal plane. This was supported by Bland-Altman-liked analysis, which showed greater variability in gait patterns among stroke patients compared to healthy individuals.

These findings suggest that further investigation could offer deeper insights into stroke-related gait impairments, which may support efforts to correct movement deviations, promote symmetry movement, and improve overall gait quality. The insights gained from this study will be useful for the design of a wearable gait feedback device to improve rehabilitation outcomes for stroke patients.

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